

DEVELOPMENT OF THE RAILWAY TRANSPORT INDUSTRY: INTERNATIONAL AND U.S. EXPERIENCE

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Abstract. The railway transport sector plays a strategic role in ensuring the sustainable development of national economies, acting not only as a logistics provider but also as a significant industrial branch. The research further analyzes the current state of Uzbekistan’s railway enterprises and identifies challenges such as technological dependence, limited modernization, and insufficient localization of production. Based on comparative analysis, policy recommendations are proposed to enhance production capacity through modernization, energy efficiency, skilled workforce development, and the establishment of public–private partnerships. The study concludes that strengthening the production potential of railway transport enterprises is a decisive factor in improving efficiency, reducing external dependence, and ensuring the long-term competitiveness of the sector in the global economy.

Key words: railway transport, production capacity, railway manufacturing, modernization, energy efficiency, localization, public–private partnership, economic development, competitiveness.

Introduction

The further development of the railway transport sector, taking into account the specific features of each transport mode as well as the strategic importance of railways in Uzbekistan, necessitates the elaboration and practical implementation of modern management approaches in transport companies. One of the main shortcomings of the domestic system is the perception of railways only as a service and logistics provider – limited to passenger and freight transportation. In reality, the railway sector also encompasses railway construction, the production of structural and repair components, and the manufacturing of freight and passenger wagons and their constituent parts within the country. Therefore, organizing localized production in railway enterprises, alongside repair activities, and introducing advanced manufacturing technologies and equipment, represent urgent and strategic tasks.

In addressing issues of production activity within railway transport enterprises, it is crucial to consider both domestic and international experiences, especially under conditions of heightened competition and growing

demands on production quality. Modern reforms in many countries demonstrate that structural transformations in the railway production sector are linked to fostering competitiveness and gradually overcoming monopolistic structures dominated by state-owned enterprises. In this process, production principles have been revised, with a growing role of competitive mechanisms leading to qualitative improvements in manufacturing processes. Consequently, studying these global trends and their applicability to Uzbekistan constitutes a key objective of the present research.

In the United States, the uninterrupted functioning of the railway system has always been directly dependent on the products and services provided by the railway manufacturing industry. Although U.S. official statistics list the railway supply industry separately, this sector integrates a wide range of activities related to the provision of products and services for railways. Since the 1850s, numerous enterprises specializing in the production of rails, rolling stock, and railway equipment have been established. Companies such as Pullman, Eagle Works, American Car Company, and Union Car Works were among the pioneers, employing hundreds of workers and supplying railway wagons and components. Illinois Central Railway opened its own workshops in Chicago in 1855, while other enterprises, such as the Chicago, Burlington & Quincy plant in Aurora, employed up to 1,300 workers by the 1870s. By the 1880s, steel plants around Chicago were producing one-third of all rails manufactured in the United States.

Pullman became globally recognized in the late 19th and early 20th centuries as the largest manufacturer of passenger and freight cars, producing up to 12,500 freight cars and 1,800 passenger cars annually by the 1890s. Alongside Pullman, many companies specialized in auxiliary products and services: Crerar, Adams & Co. produced railway lamps, Pettibone Mulliken Corporation supplied rail switches and track equipment, while Griffin Wheel Company manufactured up to 1,000 wheels per day. Moreover, the development of refrigerated cars (by Swift & Co. and Armour & Co.) and tank cars (by General American Tank Car Company) reflected the growing specialization and diversification of railway manufacturing.

The contribution of railway manufacturing and supply industries to the U.S. economy is substantial. In 2020, the sector generated USD 75.8 billion in GDP, supported 682,426 jobs, provided USD 49 billion in labor income, and accounted for USD 15.5 billion in tax revenues. These impacts can be classified into three categories:

1. **Direct impact** – GDP and jobs created by enterprises directly engaged in railway manufacturing, which amounted to USD 27.7 billion and 239,272 jobs in 2020.

2. **Indirect impact** – economic activity generated along the supply chain through procurement of components, materials, and services (e.g., wheels, signaling systems, IT, accounting), totaling USD 22.2 billion in GDP and 191,071 jobs.

3. **Induced impact** – additional GDP and employment arising from household consumption expenditures of employees in the industry and its supply chains, amounting to USD 25.9 billion in GDP and 252,082 jobs.

Overall, the total GDP contribution of USD 75.8 billion was 2.7 times greater than the direct GDP created, demonstrating a GDP multiplier of 2.7. In other words, every USD 100 of value generated in railway manufacturing creates an additional USD 170 in related sectors. Similarly, the employment multiplier of 2.9 indicates that every job in the railway manufacturing industry indirectly generates an additional 1.9 jobs in other sectors. This multiplier effect exceeds those observed in related industries, such as mechanical engineering, freight services, and ferrous metallurgy, highlighting the strategic importance of the railway manufacturing industry in ensuring the sustainable development and competitiveness of the national economy.

Table 1. The Share of Railway Enterprises in the GDP of the United States, 2022

Gross domestic product (GDP) – 75,8 billion USD		
Direct	Indirect	Induced
27,7 bn. doll	22,2 bn. doll	25,9 bn. doll
Jobs created (employment), persons – 682,426		
239 273	191 071	252 083
Labor compensation (household income) – 49,1 billion USD		
19,0 bn. doll	14,9 bn. doll	15,1 bn. doll

At present, the railway equipment manufacturing and maintenance sector in the United States is represented by a number of leading enterprises and service providers. Among them are 360 Rail Services, 3DSiteworx LLC, 3Z Automation LLC, 5280 Towing LLC, Action Towing LLC, Adams Transit LLC, Alaska Industrial Paint LLC, Albany & Eastern Railroad Company, All Aboard Washington, and Alternative Motive Power Systems. These entities operate as state-owned enterprises, public-private partnership (PPP) organizations, and private companies, thereby ensuring a diversified institutional structure of the

industry. Their activities encompass the production of railway equipment and spare parts as well as the provision of technical and logistical services, which collectively play a significant role in maintaining the sustainability and competitiveness of the U.S. railway transport sector.

Conclusion

This research confirms that the railway transport sector is not only a service provider but also a vital industrial branch with significant potential for economic growth. The analysis of international experience, particularly from the United States, shows that railway manufacturing generates strong multiplier effects on GDP, employment, and innovation, demonstrating its strategic importance for national economies.

For Uzbekistan, the findings highlight the need to expand beyond repair and logistics functions by localizing railway equipment and rolling stock production, introducing modern technologies, and strengthening public-private partnerships. Such measures will reduce external dependence, improve efficiency, and enhance competitiveness. In summary, increasing the production capacity of railway transport enterprises is a key factor for sustainable economic development, industrial modernization, and deeper integration into the global economy.

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